

The Housing Question at the Juncture of Spatial Planning and Housing Policies. A View on Romania's Political Economy Regime Changes

Enikő Vincze, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

Abstract

In the realm of housing and planning studies, the correlation between housing policies and spatial planning is seldom discussed, let alone their interconnected roles in political economy regime changes. Furthermore, a Marxist approach to the housing question is conspicuously absent from analyses placed in the context of Central and Eastern Europe. This article seeks to fill this gap by examining how planning and housing, as two constitutive factors of political economy and their linkages, facilitated the transformation of state socialism to neoliberal capitalism in Romania. The analysis was conducted using data from two research projects, which comprised statistics, legislation, development strategies, and interviews with representatives of city halls and real estate actors. After discussing the contribution of this article to the existing literature on housing and spatial planning, the second section describes how the alteration of planning and housing policies in Romania served as factors that enabled political economy transformations. In the third section, the changes at the local level are discussed, particularly in a second-tier city with regional importance. Finally, the conclusion provides a synthetic description of the interconnected conversions of spatial planning and housing policies in Romania, demonstrating the relevance of this case to the understanding of political economy regime switches through the housing question.

Keywords

Planning, housing, political economy, state socialism, neoliberal

Introduction

The article aims to fill the gap in the literature on housing and spatial planning by examining the housing question from a Marxist perspective. I argue that the housing question encompasses the political economy of housing, including housing politics that inform social and economic policies related to housing and the market relations involved in housing property, planning, production, and exchanges. Moreover, the housing question refers to the role of housing in the broader political economy regime. I specifically explore how spatial planning and housing policies are interconnected as they evolve through the historical

formations of the housing question and what their functions are in transforming state socialism into neoliberal capitalism in Romania.

This paper acknowledges the awareness that the housing question, as identified by Engels (1872) in the 19th century, i.e., the housing shortage, perpetuated through the history of capitalism and nowadays exists in the form of the scarcity of affordable homes for the many. Such a shortage is manifested in high rates of materially deprived and overcrowded dwellings, which stem from systemic factors. Traditional Marxism assumed that class exploitation only occurred in production and that only if the working class's oppression by the ruling class would be eliminated, the housing question might find a resolution. In my turn, I agree that urban space could also be exploited as a particular site of capital accumulation (Harvey, 1985), and housing-as-policy and housing-as-market are at the centre of a capitalist political economy (Aalbers and Christophers, 2014). My contribution to this field of study is examining the role of the housing sector in the changes of the political economy regime, specifically the transformation of state socialism into capitalism in an East European country.

The article follows the line of investigations, which inquired about the state's contribution to the housing crisis that unfolded in capitalism in different forms. Addressing the linkages between the 2008 financial crisis and housing policy failures, the papers of a special issue of *Housing Policy Debate* acknowledged that the encouragement of homeownership and asset-based welfare without regulating high-risk lending fuelled a housing boom and asset bubble extended far beyond the core capitalist countries (Fields & Hodkinson, 2018). The collection covered case studies from Brazil, China, Ghana, Greece, India, Ireland, Italy, Spain, and the United States but did not refer to any country from Central and Eastern Europe. Besides, these articles dealt with the relationship between economic crisis and social housing, the intensification of neoliberal policy strategies and pro-finance government interventions, informal housing and housing-related dispossessions, financing regimes and housing investors, and the evolution of homeownership and asset-based welfare from property speculation, but missed from this analytical picture the interconnected roles of spatial planning and housing policies in political economy. In contrast, my article explores them in Romania's transformation from state socialism to neoliberal capitalism, making an essential contribution to these investigations.

The empirical data that supports my analysis was collected from Romania and the city of Cluj as part of two research projects on housing and real estate development in the context of shifting political economy regimes. This data includes statistics, legislation, development strategies, and interviews with representatives of city halls and real estate actors. Romania, a former socialist country in Central and Eastern Europe, has historically been a peripheralized region until the 1800s, and it has since reached semi-periphery status (Kennedy & Smith, 1989). The state socialist plan of massive industrialization, urbanization, and public housing construction was a developmentalist project to modernize the country's predominantly rural

character inherited from the past. Since the 1990s, Romania's capitalist transformation reinforced its semi-peripheral status in the global economy, providing a cheap labour force, new markets, and opportunities for capital investments. Addressing these phenomena at local level, adds significant details about their effective impacts. I have chosen Cluj-Napoca, one of Romania's second tier cities, because similar towns are usually neglected in urban studies due to a predominant focus on the capital cities, and because it is a locality where the effects of capitalist transformations in what regards the new trends of spatial planning and housing policies are very visible. Cluj-Napoca is the seat of Cluj County located in the North-West Development Region, which was designated as one of Romania's twelve growth poles by Law 351/2001. Cluj/ Kolozsvár/ Klausenburg has been Transylvania's cultural and economic hub throughout its history. The county's industries were the fourth-largest contributors to Romania's national industrial output from 1980 to 1989. After the deep crisis during the 1990s, Cluj-Napoca recovered based on capitalist reindustrialization but also on advanced IT, financial, and professional services sectors, becoming the economically strongest and most competitive locality of the region and one of Romania's "magnet cities" (World Bank, 2017) and "competitive cities" (World Bank, 2013).

Transitioning from a mixed to a market-dominated housing regime and adopting housing ideologies that embraced homeownership was fundamental to Romania's political economy transformations (Vincze, 2017, 2022). This move allowed the market economy to function (World Bank, 1993) and integrated local real estate markets into global financialized capitalism (Aalbers, 2016; Gabor & Kohl, 2022). The Romanian governments ceased making public investments in social housing and practicing spatial planning with a predominantly public function, to facilitate the private housing sector's development, operation, and integration into a global real estate market. Additionally, municipal governments invested in enhancing urban areas regenerated for the use of social categories that could afford the rising costs of a commodified urban life and sustain the unregulated housing market. Moreover, spatial planning underwent a "de-planning" process in the context of transforming state socialism into (neoliberal) capitalism. The central state withdrew from centralized territorial systematization, and the role of local government reduced its urbanistic duties to authorize zonal-urbanistic and private construction plans to facilitate the private production of private homes. Physical persons initially produced homes for themselves or as petty-trade-in housing, followed by institutional developers producing and exchanging dwellings as a business and source for capital accumulation, and finally by developers-investors parking their "wall of money" (Aalbers, 2016) in speculative land development and housing production. This territorial de-planning process contributed to the spatialization of socio-economic disparities, with some areas benefiting from investments and others suffering from disinvestments, contributing to uneven development, an endemic feature of capitalism (Harvey, 2005; Smith, 2008).

The article is divided into four sections. The first section reviews existing literature on housing, spatial planning, and their relationship as constitutive factors of political economy regimes. The second section describes the changes in Romania's planning and housing policies as the country transitioned from state socialism to (neoliberal) capitalism. The third section examines the changes in spatial planning practices in a second-tier city in Romania during the emergence of a market-dominated housing regime. In the conclusion, I synthesize my findings on the interlinked impact of spatial planning and housing policies on the housing question and their role in political economy regime changes. I argue that this case has relevance for housing and planning studies beyond its geographic location.

Theoretical Frames to Address the Housing Question at the Juncture of Spatial Planning and Housing Policies

The housing question takes on various forms depending on the political economy regime it is embedded in. Engels coined the term in the late 19th century to describe the problem of inadequate housing and housing shortage for the working class in major urban centres. The persistent gap between the demand for homes and the supply of homes that can be built by existing financial and spatial resources reflects the continuous reproduction of this issue. To further the Marxist understanding of the housing question, it is essential to consider its own political economy, which includes relevant politics and market relations, and its role in the larger political economy regime changes. This article focuses on the linkages between housing policies and spatial planning in Romania and aims to add new knowledge and geographies to housing and planning studies from a political economy perspective.

International housing studies have produced a large amount of analysis about housing in relation to welfare regimes (Kemeny, 1995, 2001; Allen, 2006; Groves & Murie, 2007; Malpass, 2008; Ronald & Dewilde, 2017) and the role of housing in political economy (Aalbers & Christophers, 2014; Fernandez & Aalbers, 2017; Kohl & Spielau, 2022). In Central and Eastern Europe, housing literature has referred to privatisation (Anderson et al., 1997; Clapham, 1995; Clapham et al., 1996; Vincze, 2017); restitution (Chelcea, 2003; Fisher & Jaffe, 2000; Lux & Mikeszova, 2012; Lux et al., 2018); marketisation (Ionaşcu et al., 2019; Leetmaa & Bernt, 2022; Mandič, 2010; Pichler-Milanovich, 2001; Pósfai & Nagy, 2017); the strengthening of the homeownership model (Lux et al., 2021; Mandič, 2018; Soaita, 2015); emerging private rentals (Hegedüs et al., 2014; Lux & Mikeszova, 2012); housing finance (Hegedüs & Struyk, 2005; Renaud, 1996, 1999; Struyk, 2000); and financialization (Gagyi & Mikuš, 2022; Gagyi et al., 2021; Mikuš & Rodik, 2021; Florea & Dumitriu, 2022). In addition, some housing-connected studies have analyzed segregation, urban restructuring, and neighbourhood regeneration (Domburg-De Rooij & Musterd, 2002; Matznetter, 2002; Arbaci, 2007), while in CEE, similar studies have focused on gentrification/evictions/marginality (Chelcea, 2006; Chelcea et al., 2015; Lancione, 2017, 2022; Sýkora & Špačková, 2022; Zamfir,

2022; Zamfirescu & Chelcea, 2021); segregation/gated communities (Marcinićzak et al., 2014; Polanska, 2010; Rufat & Marcinićzak, 2020); and housing unevenness (Pósfai & Jelinek, 2019; Vincze & Zamfir, 2019). The present article connects to the political perspectives on housing, specifically to how state politics that informs housing policies plays a crucial role in the economy, including the economy of housing. My analysis questions the relationship of housing with planning and its role in political economy regime changes on the eastern margins of the European Union.

When it comes to planning theory, experts have noted that this field has been troubled by the fact that it is both an academic discipline and an actual profession (Holgersen, 2015). Additionally, it mixes what planners do and what should be done (Flyvbjerg, 1996). Planning as a domain of study concerns views on space, state, economy, and politics (Holgersen, 2015). Nevertheless, some planning theory takes into account more strongly the social/historical context in which planning occurs (Healey, 2007), while others, like communicative planning theory, have a poor understanding of how planning is intertwined with power and social relations (Holgersen, 2015) and it ends up obscuring and facilitating the dominant ideology of market forces (Gunder, 2010). Scholars have observed that the neoliberal entrepreneurial ethos has not only permeated the economy but also urban planning in late capitalism (Sager, 2011; Harvey, 1989). A profound spatial planning skepticism (re)emerged across Northwestern Europe (Olesen, 2014). Since the 1980s, the neoliberalization of planning has taken place very differently across time and space (Peck and Tickell, 2002), and changes in planning systems and practices varied nationally during different waves of neoliberalization. However, these processes displayed some common trends, such as the depoliticization of planning and strong links with collaborative planning ideals (Olesen, 2014). My article addresses the role of planning, linked with housing policies, in transforming state socialism into (neoliberal) capitalism in Romania. This analysis is facilitated by approaches that integrate Marxist critique of political economy with analysis of spatial planning (Fairclough et al., 2002) and recognize that every form of production creates its form of government, so planning itself is embedded within a system defined by capital accumulation (Holgersen, 2020). While existing studies highlights the transformation of industrial/Fordist and Keynesian cities into post-industrial and entrepreneurial cities in capitalist countries, my analysis observes the transformation of state socialist cities and planning systems into capitalist ones informed by neoliberal ideologies.

The divorce of planning from a focus on housing presents a puzzle because the two have been historically linked in Europe. Western European governments entered the housing field before or during WWI and have remained in it to varying degrees until today (Marcuse, 1980). The divorce might be explained, among other factors, by the desire to enhance real estate values and accommodate the changing demands of business enterprises in the city (Marcuse, 1980, p.166). Marcuse also noted that when the dangers to public health and political stability

of poor housing were pressing, city planning was preoccupied with providing adequate housing for the working class, but when this pressure receded, planning was divorced from such concerns. Recent literature links urban/spatial planning to housing matters (Gurran and Bramley, 2017) by observing how the evolution of modern city planning is related to housing reforms, how policy interventions are connected to housing strategies and market characteristics through the planning system, how planning always involves the exercise of powers vested in the government, for example regarding the regulation of private property for public purposes. These investigations also reveal that the role of the state and planners has evolved historically. They stress that there is a need to explore the impact of land use planning systems on housing supply, and, beyond the limited neoliberal view, which argues for less regulation, to recognize that governments should mobilize many other strategies to overcome the shortage of affordable housing (Gurran and Phibbs, 2013). Contributing to existing analysis, my article examines the role of housing policies and spatial planning in Romania's political economy changes, recognizing that their linkages are constitutive factors in this transformation.

For the purposes of my paper, I define spatial planning as the “complex processes of regulating land use that (often) ends with a decision as to where (not) to place what” (Holgersen, 2015, p. 6), including dwellings, and recognize that these procedures are connected to larger mechanisms of urban and political economy formations. I also believe that housing and spatial planning policies are political instruments that sustain the socioeconomic and territorial development trends of a political economy regime. Moreover, I maintain that both territorial planning and housing policies are shaped by political ideologies (Shore & Wright, 1997, 2011). It is important to note that governmental policies are not technologically neutral instruments used to solve problems through legislation and institutions; rather, decision-makers use them to develop and implement solutions based on how they politically define the issues, identify their causes, and comprehend their solutions. In particular, my analysis focuses on the politics of housing policies connected to the politics of spatial planning, which become more discernible when comparisons are made across historical periods (Jacobs and Manzi, 2016). The historical periods my article targets are state socialism and (neoliberal) capitalism, with a geographical focus on Romania. The central question is the role that the studied linkages play in political economy regime changes.

The Role of Housing Policies and Spatial Planning in Political Economy Regime (Changes) in Romania

During state socialism, the production, distribution, and exchange of housing in Romania were carried out within centralized planning of industrialisation and urbanisation processes. Housing policies played a role in the socialist political economy by ensuring financially accessible housing for the workforce that migrated to urban areas where state-owned

industrial enterprises created millions of new jobs. The socialist urbanization plans followed the territorial systematization policies that aimed for cohesion between and within cities. All interventions (industrial development, internal migration, housing, educational and healthcare services, and cultural and sports facilities) were coordinated across economic sectors and territories using the tools provided by Law 8/1972 on the Planned Socioeconomic Development of Romania and Law 58/1974 on Systematization. Due to the high cost of socialist developmentalism, the Romanian government allowed the formation of a mixed housing regime in which state-owned residences coexisted with homes owned by cooperatives or in personal property. The state controlled the latter forms of ownership to prevent the transformation of dwellings into tradable commodities. This mixed regime was founded on the constitutional recognition of the right to personal property without acknowledging the universal right to housing. In practice, however, access to the home was contingent on employment, and full employment was regarded as a societal and individual necessity.

Between 1966 and 1977, the Romanian state constructed 1,733,894 new apartments covering both urban and rural areas using state funds or population funds with state support. The plan in the mid-1970s was to accelerate the construction of blocs of flats to realize an additional 2,500,000 – 3,000,000 apartments by 1990, to cover the existing demands or respond to the needs of labourers. Between 1951 and 1989, the state constructed 2,984,083 homes (Anuarul Statistic al României 1990, p.520). This became possible due to a socialist financial system backed up by a mechanism through which the state managed to direct financial resources into a centralized pocket and redistribute them across the sectors and domains of the national economy and territories. In socialism, the surplus value created by the labour force was used to finance investments into goods that the population could consume collectively (schools, hospitals, housing, cultural institutions, sports facilities) and to supply means for further economic activities, ensuring long-term socio-economic development. Eventually, in socialism, it was not only its salary but also the collective consumption of goods and economic growth that benefited the labour force. The new value created by the labour that people were expected to perform for the benefit of society (besides the labour for itself, for which they received salaries) contributed to the social consumption fund and the country's economic development or accumulation fund. The labour force's access to collective consumption goods, including housing, at lower prices or for free was not about state generosity. Rather, the workers were entitled to public housing because their labour force created surplus value that they were not directly compensated for. The state administered and redistributed this surplus value to ensure economic production and larger social reproduction.

During state socialism, the costs of construction, including the building of industrial facilities, residential units, and socio-cultural edifices, were considered major investments, alongside the production or purchase of new means of production for manufacturing and providing means for extractive industries (Economie Politică, 1978, p.381). The costs of

building new housing were also considered investments to produce homes as consumption goods needed for individual and societal reproduction. The socialist economy viewed production and consumption as interdependent economic processes. Therefore, investments in home-making were regarded as a productive activity that created state-owned houses as collective consumption goods, which was not contradictory. Even though housing was part of the collective consumption goods that the state provided from the state budget to respond to the fundamental need for housing, its related costs were covered by both the social consumption fund and the accumulation fund dedicated to economic development. The rents supported by state enterprises and the reparations of state-owned housing given for use by the workers were delivered from the social consumption fund, along with the costs of urban public infrastructure including sanitation, public lighting, and repairs to roads or bridges (Economie Politică, 1978, p.397-398). The accumulation or economic development fund covered the costs of constructing new homes or extending the existing housing stock (idem, p.376).

In socialism, state-owned homes were created and distributed within a hierarchical institutional system. First, the factories communicated their housing needs to the Ministry of People's Councils, which requested funds from the Central Planning Committee and communicated with the county-level state administration institutions. Then, the county institutions allocated the constructed housing units to the People's Local Councils, whose executive committees did the concrete work of distributing the apartments in blocks of flats among state enterprises and institutions. The latter allocated them to their employees based on the decisions of the Working People's Council and trade unions. Finally, the state-owned housing stock was administered by the Urban Management Enterprise. In parallel with the mechanism described above, there was also top-down planning; the Central Planning Committee announced to the local councils and construction companies the number of new housing units to be built in different localities according to centralized plans of industrial developments across the country. The local organizations had to follow the directives coming from the centre, but at times localities could not use all the funds they were allocated for the construction of new housing units; when this occurred, in the last trimester of the year, the unused funds were redistributed among those cities that reached the planned target and needed more construction than initially stipulated.

During state socialism, the state also supported the construction of privately owned homes by offering land, logistics, and cheap loans, besides building homes for sale to reduce housing production costs from the state budget. Housing construction was a productive economic sector that consumed goods produced by various industries and was a significant pillar of the construction sector and an important job-creator. From 1951 to 1989, 5.6 million new residences were built in Romania, almost three million financed by the state (53.98%). Most were rented to tenants at modest rates, while the state sold 411,584 units (14%) to higher-income residents. The mixed-housing property regime at the national level contained a large

percentage of homeowners (67%) due to Romania's rural population being 43.6% of the total population until 1990. In these terms, there was a rupture between urban and rural Romania, with the former having a higher rate of homes that were public property or public rentals (57% of the total).

In the aftermath of the regime change, the Romanian government implemented the right-to-buy and retrocession laws, which fully privatized the state-owned housing stock. Housing played a crucial role in the political economy via the early privatization of the housing sector. In line with the World Bank and International Monetary Fund's loan agreements with the Romanian government, the political decision-makers used the privatization and unregulated commodification of the housing sector to establish the capitalist market economy. Alongside the right-to-buy and retrocession laws, the government also promoted homeownership, private construction, the mortgage system, and the state's withdrawal from public social housing production. These policy changes coincided with the privatization of industrial enterprises, public administration's decentralization, price liberalization, market deregulation, land and bank privatization. Additionally, the government utilized spatial planning and land use (de)regulation to serve the interests of capital accumulation.

Romania's government abandoned central planning after 1990. Although new urbanism was only put into effect in 2001 through the "Law for Land Use and Urban Planning," the systematization law was one of the first old regulations abolished in December 1989. This abandonment of the planning system led to increased disparities between Romanian regions, counties, and municipalities, as territorial development was subordinated to capital investment interests. Romania also adopted local autonomy through "the public authorities . . . such as the elected local councils and mayors" under Law 215/2001 in response to its obligations as a Council of Europe member state. Law 195/2006 described decentralization as "the transfer of administrative and financial powers from the central to the local government." Romania's Territorial Development Strategy (TDS) was initiated in 2012 to enhance the country's long-term integration into global development and international markets. However, the government only adopted the TDS in 2016, in the context of the new Partnership Agreement of Romania with the European Union (EU), which contained significant provisions on territorial cohesion, the urban dimension of cohesion policy, certain macro-regional strategies, and integrated territorial interventions for urban development and community-led local development. The TDS upheld the so-called polycentric developmental paradigm, which viewed major metropolitan areas as growth poles that were expected to stimulate development in their surrounding areas. However, the TDS failed to counterbalance the persistent and expanding territorial disparities generated by the capitalist political economy, resulting in uneven development.

The systemic shift from state socialism to capitalism occurred when neoliberalism became the dominant economic ideology worldwide. Romania's mixed housing regime was

transformed into a market-dominated system, where housing became a domain for capital accumulation and profit-making business. The housing regime was overtaken by real estate development and used as a core element of the secondary circuit of capital. These developments in the housing system contributed to the emergence of a capitalist class and the stratification of labour classes. Opportunities for foreign investment emerged in residential real estate, retail, office building, and logistics sectors as the country became more open to the unrestricted movement of capital across borders.

After 1990, transformational ideologies – mostly based on budgetary restrictions that threatened the ongoing expansion of the public housing sector – questioned the state's ability to guarantee and properly administer dwellings for its residents. The general justification for changing the housing regime was the failure of the socialist economy. In addition, the housing market was deregulated to put a stop to the much-criticized centralized economy. Nonetheless, the Romanian government launched two public housing programs in the late 1990s. The first program, according to Housing Law 446/1996, gave local public administration institutions control over the creation and ownership of new social housing (which cannot be sold), but they were not held liable for ensuring that the available housing stock was responding to actual needs. However, local governments rarely request extra funding from the National Social Housing Program. Under this scheme, only 90 social apartment buildings with 3,911 social apartments were built in the country between 2007 and 2012, as stated in the National Housing Strategy for 2022-50, enacted by Governmental Decision 842/2022. The second program, since the National Housing Agency (NHA) was established by Law 152/1998, has built a new type of publicly funded housing specifically for people under 35 whose salaries are below the national average. As a result of this law, only 34,000 NHA apartments have been built in the country, of which 6,000 have been sold to eligible renters. According to Governmental Decision 1237/2008, between 2015 and 2022, the NHA was supposed to build 300 apartments for Roma people in Romania; however, they only delivered 239.

As a result of the transformation of the housing regime, the share of public and social housing in Romania has dropped to below 2%, with only a slight variation between different cities. This percentage is significantly lower than the average social rent rate between 1992 and 2002 (20.7%) in countries with a capitalist statist-developmental welfare regime (such as France, Austria, Sweden, Finland, and Japan). Furthermore, the homeownership rate in Romania has risen to over 95%, which is higher than the 70.1% average rate of homeownership measured between 1992 and 2002 in countries with a market welfare regime, such as the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, and Norway (Schwartz and Seebrooke, 2009). While the Romanian housing sector has made substantial progress in eradicating the legacy of state socialism, the welfare regimes of advanced capitalist countries continue to retain remnants of their post-war housing policies.

Changing Patterns of Spatial Planning and Housing Development in Cluj-Napoca

Historical figures portray Cluj's development during the past century. In 1941, only about 1,810 hectares of land were used to house 114,984 people. The city expanded significantly until 1977, reaching a total area of 6,470 hectares and a population of 262,858 residing in 70,865 dwellings. Cluj-Napoca's population and housing stock continued to grow until 1992, with a population of 311,674 people and 113,159 homes. Further on, the population increased by about 10,000 between 1992 and 2016, while the city's territory grew to 10,472 hectares as former agricultural fields were absorbed to construct new urban districts.

In response to the demands of socialist industrialization and re-urbanization, the first novel workers' districts (Grigorescu and Gheorgheni) were built in the 1960s. To accommodate the additional 100,000 residents of Cluj employed by new industrial jobs, even larger neighbourhoods of blocs of flats were constructed in the 1970s and 1980s (Mărăști and Mănăștur). These new districts extended beyond the original city limits, necessitating the demolition of old rural housing stock on the city's outskirts ((Hofstadts), which formerly provided agricultural products for the town.

Currently, Cluj-Napoca is marketed as the Heart of Transylvania, a cosmopolitan European city and an important destination for business in South-Eastern Europe, a city with a remarkable potential for foreign investments (Cluj Business). According to the report *Economia Clujului (2020)*, 53.7% of the over 204,000 workers were employed in the service sector in 2010, and this sector's contribution to added value in the local economy increased from 25% to over 35%. In 2018, Cluj-Napoca was recognized as a technology hub nicknamed the Silicon Valley of Eastern Europe (The Mayor.eu). In 2021, it ranked first in smart city development and eighth in friendliness to business in the perception-based survey conducted among countries named Emerging Europe, performing well among the non-capital localities (Emerging Europe, 2021). Since 2020, the World Bank has been closely collaborating with the municipality to prepare the Integrated Urban Development Strategy 2021-2030 for the Cluj Metropolitan Area (SIDU 2030), with a clear objective of achieving climate neutrality by 2030, and has developed one of the world's first NetZeroCity Action Plans, not only in Europe but in the world (Ionescu-Heroiu, 2023).

The initiatives mentioned above may suggest that there has been a considerable amount of planning regarding the economic development and international promotion of the city. However, the introductory paragraphs of SIDU 2030 urge a more careful planning. The reason for this was that in the Cluj Metropolitan Area the fast economic growth between 2000 and 2017 (by more than 3.3 times) led to negative consequences such as chaotic urban development, pollution, congestion, rising prices, and cost of living. The World Bank's SIDU 2030 Housing Strategy for the Cluj-Napoca City Hall confirmed the lack of planning even more explicitly: with "moderate population growth, but significant compared to all other large

urban agglomerations in Romania that are facing population decline, ... topographic constraints (hilly terrain, landslide risk). ... and height restrictions on the east (due to airport) ..., in Cluj-Napoca have contributed to sprawl and fragmented development in the surrounding villages with urban planning left behind (World Bank, 2021).

After 1990, in the context of capitalist deindustrialization, economic restructuring, and private housing production, residential real estate development followed three spatial paradigms in Cluj-Napoca (Figure 1):

1. The city continued to expand its intraurban perimeter by constructing new neighbourhoods, including both family homes and collective real estate. This led to the emergence of several novel districts, such as Bună Ziua, Sopor, Borhanci, Becaş, Făget, and Câmpului, which contributed to doubling the city's built environment by the end of the 1990s.

2. New residential development projects were integrated into the old socialist districts during the early 2000s, before the 2008 financial crisis. Examples of these projects include River Tower in Iris, Grand Park Residence in Gheorgheni, Tower Park in Mănăştur, American Village Condominiums in Grigorescu, and Central Park Residence in Plopilor.

3. A trend that began earlier but strengthened mostly after 2015 was the return to semi-central areas and the regeneration of brownfields and zones with low-quality edifices, resulting in new office buildings, residential towers, and buildings with mixed functions. For instance, the Sports Hall Residence was constructed on the premises of the former silk factory România Muncitoare, while the Platinia Mall was built on the former site of the Ursus Bear factory. Other examples include Scala Residence, Maurer Panoramic, Oxygen Mall, EBS Real Estate, and Marina Properties, which were built on the premises of the former Flacăra, Napochim, and Abator plants. Additionally, The Office was constructed on the prior platform of the Someşul knitwear factory, and Liberty Residential was built near the earlier Liberty Technology Park, on the premises of the former Libertatea furniture factory.

Figure 1 - Spatial patterns of residential real estate development on the map of Cluj-Napoca

Almost all of Cluj-Napoca's former industrial platforms are now the location of new real estate developments, except for the over 100 hectares of the former CUG (heavy-machine manufacturing plant), the pharmaceutical company Terapia, both located in the city's north-east, and the Farmec cosmetics factory, placed in a semi-central area undergoing urban regeneration. Most of the investors in residential real estate are of Romanian origin, with some exceptions, such as the Belgian Speedwell, American White Star Real Estate, French Bina Real Estate, and the South-African Prime Kapital, which have lately announced plans to join the residential real estate ventures. In contrast, foreign investment funds constructed the vast majority of the retail and office buildings, with a few projects built with capital investment from Romanian companies, such as Iulius Grup (Iași), Polus Real Estate (Cluj), Platina Group (Satu Mare), and Pavăl Holding (Bacău). International investment firms, such as BlackRock (via NEPI Rockcastle), New Europe Property Investments (NEPI), White Star Real Estate, and the British Investment Fund First Property, have recently completed large transactions involving office buildings in Cluj-Napoca that contain outsourced IT and engineering research companies.

In addition to the three spatial patterns discussed above, there is a fourth territorial arrangement seen in residential real estate development that aims to meet the housing demands of the low-middle classes drawn to Cluj by the revitalized industrial and service sectors. This pattern features new properties in the neighbouring villages of the Cluj

metropolitan area. The metropolization paradigm started in the 1990s, and as Figure 2 shows, it has greatly increased between 2006 and 2014, with more homes created in the nearby five villages than in the entire city. This trend has persisted after 2015. However, during the post-crisis recovery phase, more new private homes were constructed in semi-central Cluj-Napoca, especially in the smaller and larger residences erected on brownfields.

Figure 2 - Number of finalized homes in Cluj-Napoca and five neighbouring villages from Cluj Metropolitan Area, the author, Source: INS Tempo online

Furthermore, the evolution of housing stock in Cluj-Napoca is reflected in Figures 3 and 4, which show the total number of completed homes and the number of existing homes, both overall and on private property, between 1993 and 2021. The previous economic crisis recovery period facilitated the rise in newly constructed private housing units, especially considering that neither the municipality nor the state built a single social housing unit during this time. Access to a home has become almost exclusively provided through the unregulated market, making the city's housing stock a financial asset with promising real estate returns. In line with Figure 5, the average housing market prices increased from 800 euros per square meter in 2008 to 2,400 euros per square meter in 2023. As a result, Cluj now has a higher home price index than both Bucharest, the nation's capital, and the average of all cities in Romania (Figures 6 and 7), making it Romania's most expensive city.

Figure 3 - Number of finalized homes, total and from private funds, Cluj-Napoca, 1995-2021, the author, Source: INS, Tempo online

Figure 4 - Number of existing homes, total and in private property, Cluj-Napoca, 1993-2021, the author, Source: INS, Tempo online

Figure 5 - Housing price index in Cluj-Napoca, Source: Imobiliare.ro, accessed May 10, 2023

Figure 6 - Housing price index in Bucharest, Source: Imobiliare.ro, accessed May 10, 2023

Figure 7 - Housing price index, Romanian average, Source: Imobiliare.ro, accessed May 10, 2023

The assetization of homes or their transformation into an object of financial investment is reflected in Table 1. This table shows a high number of physical or juridical persons who, in 2020, owned more than one residential property in Cluj-Napoca, according to the evidence of the tax directorate of the City Hall. These numbers suggest that rentierism is an option for several people who own more than one housing unit, which they might use as a source of (complementary) income. In 2020, 46,078 physical persons who owned more than one residential unit in Cluj-Napoca were identified, many of whom could have been used for rental purposes. Unfortunately, there is inadequate information available in Romania to determine how many people live in private rentals. While official statistics show as low as 3% of the population living in private rentals, estimates place the rate in major cities like Cluj-Napoca as high as 15% (National Housing Strategy, 2022, p.28).

	Physical persons	Juridical persons	Total
Number of owners with more than one apartment in collective housing	5,644	462	6,106
Number of owners with more than one family house	40,434	3,800	44,234
Total number of owners with more than one residential unit	46,078	4,262	50,340

Table 1 - Number of owners with more than one residential unit, Cluj-Napoca, 2020, Source: Cluj-Napoca City Hall dataset

As the housing market expanded without regulation and urban planning was put in the service of private interests, new residential real estate developments emerged throughout Cluj-Napoca and its neighbouring villages. This type of development also resulted in the largest racialized and ghettoized territory in Romania (Vincze & Zamfir, 2019). Pata Rât,

located on the city's eastern outskirts near the landfills, is not a totally new phenomenon. But it was inhabited only by one Roma community from the 1970s to the 1990s, who settled there for informal waste selection at the city's old garbage dump. In the 2000s, the area grew to accommodate about 2,000 people because the City Hall redirected hundreds of Roma families evicted from other areas undergoing urban regeneration to Pata Rât.

The prevalence of spatial de-planning after 1990 was directly related to adopting neoliberal housing policies in Cluj-Napoca and the city's subsequent rise to the top of the housing market price rankings. In recent years, however, the municipality has established some tentative requirements in the process of authorizing new construction and zonal urbanistic plans. This is because chaotic private development had created enormous problems in spatial mobility and traffic, and the City Hall was ready to integrate into its pro-growth discourse the climate-related EU demands. The City Hall has also begun consultations for a possible controlled urbanistic plan to regenerate the city's largest brownfield and has created a so-called master plan for another emerging neighbourhood. However, although the regulatory standards exist, they are not consistently put into practice, and the city's proclaimed urban regeneration policy in all city districts keeps paving the way for profit-making via real estate development.

Conclusions

My article addressed the housing question at the juncture of spatial planning and housing policies as they evolved in two historical periods (state socialism and (neoliberal) capitalism). By focusing on Romania and one of its economically most advanced second-tier cities, Cluj-Napoca, I aimed to answer the question regarding their role in political economy regime changes.

The socialist housing regime produced and distributed homes via an overarching territorial planning system and housing policies to support the country's socio-economic development (plans). Consequently, the urban housing stock provided for the labour force was distributed territorially to ensure balanced development at various levels and respond to the needs of socialist industrialisation. To pave the way for the emergence of the private sector and the unregulated market across all spheres of society as conditions for the formation of a capitalist political economy in this country, the Romanian state dismantled the socialist economy and its related housing and planning system. This involved de-planning and withdrawing from housing provision while implementing supportive (among others, fiscal and territorial) measures for private residential real estate development. Spatial planning became a tool for serving private interests, with private residential buildings built on private lands to serve profit-making priorities.

The privatization of housing in the 1990s, the creation of legal frames that transformed cities into growth engines and autonomous administrative units, and the promotion of a

polycentric development model encouraging magnet and competitive cities to supposedly radiate development in nearby territories were all crucial state interventions in the formation of capitalism in Romania. While most areas across the country went through a heavy population loss and many cities shrank due to reduced capital accumulation interests, the regional towns started attracting private investors and a labour force in need of new homes. The existing housing stock in these cities became insufficient to meet rising demand, while the new demands were also investment-related. Additionally, municipalities contributed to new real estate developments via urban regeneration programs implemented around former industrial platforms when the privatized lands of the magnet cities could not support more construction via urban sprawl. At the same time, a metropolization process also started to evolve, with surrounding villages providing peri-urban spaces, responding to the housing needs of people drawn to the regional cities' expanding economies. People's migration from a city toward its metropolitan area, that is, into villages undergoing novel urbanization, constituted a search for new residential spaces and a reaction to the rising cost of living in the cities. These moves were lower-income people's response to the full marketization, super-commodification, and financialization of housing.

Local governments have only recently begun to consider constraining the intense real estate growth and compelling developers to observe regulations for public benefits, as cities and their peri-urban surroundings have become swamped by chaotic real estate development. In Cluj-Napoca, recent efforts have aimed to rebalance private and public interests by conditioning new authorizations on constructing roads and kindergartens in new residential real estate areas. However, this approach falls short of acknowledging the need to reconnect planning and housing policies to solve the housing question by responding to effective housing needs through a substantial public housing stock.

The logic of the market and capital accumulation leads to an unequal distribution of private dwellings across different territories and social classes. In neoliberal capitalism, urban development is not planned with public welfare in mind, which means that public housing and social infrastructure are not always located near people's workplaces. As a result, urban spatial planning is divorced from housing policies, and housing production and distribution are no longer guided by the public functions of spatial planning. However, one can view this situation differently: spatial planning and housing policies have been reconnected under the framework of privatization, commodification, and financialization of housing and urban space, which support market-dominated housing and planning regimes as pillars of a political economy led by the interests of capital accumulation.

Acknowledgements

The article was written with the support of the research project “Precarious labour and peripheral housing. Context of changing industrial relations and uneven territorial development,” Research Grant Contract: 22 from 01/11/2020 (RO-NO-2019-0496).

References

- Aalbers, M.B., & Christophers, B. (2014) (2014) Centring Housing in Political Economy, *Housing, Theory and Society* 31(4), 373-394. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2014.947082>
- Aalbers, M.B. (2016) *The Financialization of Housing. A political economy approach*, Routledge.
- Aalbers, M.B. (2017) The Variegated Financialization of Housing. Symposium introduction, *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* 41(4), 542-554.
- Allen, J. (2006) Welfare Regimes, Welfare Systems and Housing in Southern Europe, *European Journal of Housing Policy* 6(3), 251-277. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616710600973102>
- Anderson, R. E., Dejanokov, S., Pohl, G., & Claessons, S. (1997). Privatization and restructuring in Central and Eastern Europe. *Viewpoint: Public policy for the private sector*. Note no. 123. World Bank.
- Arbaci, S. (2007). Ethnic Segregation, Housing Systems and Welfare Regimes in Europe. *European Journal of Housing Policy* 7(4), 401-433. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616710701650443>
- Brenner, N. (2009) Urban Governance and the Production of New State Spaces in Western Europe, 1960–2000. In B. Arts, A. Lagendijk and H. von Houtum (eds.), *The Disoriented State: Shifts in Governmentality, Territoriality and Governance. Environment & Policy*, vol 49, Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-9480-4_3
- Chelcea, L. (2003). Ancestors, domestic groups, and the socialist state: Housing nationalization and restitution in Romania. *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 45(4), 714–740. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0010417503000331>
- Chelcea, L. (2006). Marginal Groups in Central Places: Gentrification, Property Rights and Post-socialist Primitive Accumulation (Bucharest, Romania). In E. György & Z. Kovács (Eds.), *Social Changes and Social Sustainability in Historical Urban Centres: The Case of Central Europe* (pp. 127-147). Pecs: Centre for Regional Studies of Hungarian Academy of Sciences.
- Chelcea, L., Popescu, R., & Cristea, D. (2015). Who are the gentrifiers and how do they change central city neighbourhoods? Privatization, commodification, and gentrification in Bucharest. *Geografie* 120(2), 113–133. <https://doi.org/10.37040/geografie2015120020113>
- Clapham, D., Hegedüs, J., Kintrea, K., Kay, H., & Tosics, I. (1996). *Housing privatization in Eastern Europe*. Greenwood Publishing Group.
- Clapham, D. (1995) Privatisation and the East European Housing Model, *Urban Studies* 32 (4-5), 679-694, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00420989550012834>
- Cristea, M., Mare, C., Moldovan, C., Andreea-Mirela China, A.M., Farole, T., Vințan, A., Park, J., Garrett, K.P., & Ionescu-Heroiu, M. (2017) *Magnet Cities. Migration and Commuting in Romania*. Available at <https://elibrary.worldbank.org/doi/abs/10.1596/27874>. Accessed May 10, 2023.
- Domburg-De Rooij, T., & Musterd S. (2002). *Ethnic Segregation and the Welfare State*. Routledge.
- Engels, F. (1872) *The Housing question*. Leipzig Volksstaat. Available at - <https://www.marxists.org/archive/marx/works/1872/housing-question/>. Accessed May 10, 2023.

- Fernandez, R., & Aalbers, M.B. (2017) Housing and capital in the 21st century: realigning housing studies and political economy, *Housing, Theory and Society* 34(2), 151-158. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2017.1293379>.
- Fields, D.J., & Hodkinson, S.N. (2018) Housing policy in crisis: an international perspective. *Housing Policy Debate* 28(1), 1-5.
- Fisher, L. M., & Jaffe, A. J. (2000). Restitution in transition countries. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment* 15(3), 233–248. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1010141604092>
- Florea, I., & Dumitriu, M. (2022) Different Debtors, Different Struggles: Foreign-Currency Housing Loans and Class Tensions in Romania. *Critical Housing Analysis* 9 (1), 68-77. <https://doi.org/10.13060/23362839.2022.9.1.542>
- Gabor, D., & Kohl, S. (2022) *My home is an asset class. Study about the financialization of housing in Europe*.
- Gagyí, Á., & Mikuš, M. (2022). Housing finance in the aftermath of the foreign-currency mortgage crisis in Eastern Europe: Editorial. *Critical Housing Analysis* 9(1), 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.13060/23362839.2022.9.1.539>
- Gagyí, Á., Jelinek, C., Pósfai, Z., & Vígvári, A. (2021). Semi-peripheral financialization and informal household solutions. Embedded scales of uneven development in Hungarian urban fringes. In M. Mikuš & P. Rodik (Eds.), *Households and financialization in Europe. Mapping variegated patterns in semiperipheries* (pp. 81-104). Routledge.
- Groves, R., & Murie, A. (2007). Housing and the new welfare state: *Perspectives from East Asia and Europe*. Routledge.
- Gurran, N., & Bramley, G. (2017) *Urban planning and the housing market. International perspectives for policy and practice*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Gurran, N., & Phibbs, P. (2014) Housing supply and urban planning reform: the recent Australian experience, 2003-2012. *International Journal of Housing Policy* 13(4), 381-407.
- Hall, T., & Hubbard, P. (1996) The entrepreneurial city: new urban politics, new urban geographies? *Progress in Human Geography* 20(2), 153–174. <https://doi.org/10.1177/030913259602000201>
- Harvey, D. (1989) From Managerialism to Entrepreneurialism: The Transformation in Urban Governance in Late Capitalism. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography* 71(1), 3-17, <https://doi.org/10.1080/04353684.1989.11879583>
- Harvey, D. (1985) *The urbanization of capital. Studies in the history and theory of capitalist urbanization*. John Hopkins University Press.
- Harvey, D. (2005) *Spaces of Neoliberalization: Towards a Theory of Uneven Geographical Development*. Franz Steiner Verlag.
- Hegedüs, J., & Struyk, R. (2005). *Housing finance. New and old models in Central Europe, Russia, and Kazakhstan*. Open Society Institute.
- Holgersen S. (2015) Spatial planning as condensation of social relations: A dialectical approach. *Planning Theory* 14(1), 5–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2427.12522>
- Holgersen, S. (2020) On Spatial Planning and Marxism: Looking Back, Going Forward. *Antipode* 52(3), 800-824. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12614>
- Jacobs, K., & Pawson, H. (2015) Introduction to the special edition: ‘The politics of housing policy’. *Housing Studies* 30(5), 651-655.
- Jacobs, K., & Manzi, T. (2016) ‘The party’s over’: critical junctures, crises and the politics of housing policy. *Housing Studies* 32(1), 17-34.

- Ionaşcu, E., de La Paz, P. T., & Mironiuc, M. (2019). The relationship between housing prices and market transparency. Evidence from the metropolitan European markets. *Housing, Theory and Society* 38(1), 42–71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2019.1672577>
- Ionescu-Heroiu, M. (2023): *Cluj-Napoca: Seven steps toward climate neutrality by 2030*. Available at <https://blogs.worldbank.org/sustainablecities/cluj-napoca-seven-steps-toward-climate-neutrality-2030>. Accessed May 10, 2023.
- Kemeny, J. (1995). *From Public Housing to the Social Market: Rental Policy Strategies in Comparative Perspective*. Routledge.
- Kohl, S., & Spielau, A. (2022) Centring construction in the political economy of housing: variegated growth regimes after the Keynesian construction state. *Cambridge Journal of Economics* 46(3), 465–490. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cje/beac015>
- Lancione, M. (2017). Revitalising the uncanny: Challenging inertia in the struggle against forced evictions. *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space* 35(6), 1012–1032. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263775817701731>
- Lancione, M. (2022). Inhabiting Dispossession in the Post-Socialist City: Race, Class and the Plan in Bucharest, Romania. *Antipode*. 10.1111/anti.12821
- Leetmaa, K., & Bernt, M. (2022). Special issue Intro: Housing estates in the era of marketization – Governance practices and urban planning. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-022-09976-8>
- Lux, M., & Mikeszova, M. (2012). Property restitution and private rental housing in transition: The case of the Czech Republic. *Housing Studies* 27(1), 77–96. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2012.629643>
- Lux, M., Cirman, A., Kährlik, A., & Miaskowska-Daszkiwicz, K. (2018). Property restitution after 1990. In J. Hegedüs, M. Lux, & V. Horváth (Eds.), *Private Rental Housing in Transition Countries* (pp. 71–97). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Lux, M., Sunega, P., & Kázmér, L. (2021). Intergenerational financial transfers and indirect reciprocity: Determinants of the reproduction of homeownership in the post-socialist Czech Republic. *Housing Studies* 36(8), 1294–1317.
- Malpass, P. (2008) Housing and the New Welfare State: Wobbly Pillar or Cornerstone?, *Housing Studies* 23(1), 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673030701731100>
- Mandič, S. (2010). The changing role of housing assets in post-socialist countries. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment* 25(2), 213–226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-010-9186-5>
- Mandič, S. (2018). Motives for home ownership: Before and after the transition. *Housing, Theory and Society* 35(3), 281–299. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2017.1329164>
- Marcińczak, S., Gentile, M., Rufat, S., & Chelcea, L. (2014). Urban geographies of hesitant transition: Tracing socioeconomic segregation in post-ceaşescu Bucharest. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* 38(4), 1399–1417. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2427.12073>
- Marcuse, P. (1980) Housing in early city planning. *Journal of Urban History* 6(2), 153-176.
- Mikuš, M., & Rodik, P. (2021). *Households and financialization in Europe. Mapping variegated patterns in semiperipheries*. Routledge.
- Matznetter, W. (2002). Social Housing Policy in a Conservative Welfare State: Austria as an Example. *Urban Studies* 39(2), 265-282. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00420980120102966>
- Olesen, K. (2014) The neoliberalsation of strategic urban planning. *Planning Theory* 13(3), 288-303.
- Peck, J. (2014) Entrepreneurial urbanism: between uncommon sense and dull compulsion. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography* 96(4), 396-401. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geob.12061>

- Pichler-Milanovich, N. (2001). Urban housing markets in central and Eastern Europe: Convergence, divergence or policy 'collapse.' *European Journal of Housing Policy* 1(2), 145–187. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616710110083416>
- Polanska, D. V. (2010). The emergence of gated communities in post-communist urban context: And the reasons for their increasing popularity. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment* 25(3), 295–312. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-010-9189-2>
- Pósfai, Zs., & Nagy, G. (2017). Crisis and the reproduction of core-periphery relations on the Hungarian housing market. *European Spatial Research and Policy* 24(2), 17–38. <https://doi.org/10.1515/esrp-2017-0007>
- Pósfai, Zs., & Jelinek, C. (2019). Reproducing Socio-Spatial Unevenness Through the Institutional Logic of Dual Housing Policies in Hungary, in Lang, T. & Görmar, F. (Eds.) *Regional and Local Development in Times of Polarisation. New Geographies of Europe* (pp. 197-223). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-1190-1_9
- Renaud, B. (1996). *Housing finance in transition economies: The early years in Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union*. The World Bank, Financial Sector Development Department.
- Renaud, B. (1999). The Financing of Social Housing in Integrating Financial Markets: A View from Developing Countries. *Urban Studies* 36 (4), 755-773. <http://10.1080/0042098993448>
- Ronald, R., & Dewilde, C. (2017) *Housing Wealth and Welfare*. EE Elgar online. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781785360961>
- Rufat, S., & Marcińczak, S. (2020). The equalising mirage? Socioeconomic segregation and environmental justice in post-socialist Bucharest. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment* 35(3), 917–938. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-019-09722-7>
- Soaita, A. M. (2015). The meaning of home in Romania: Views from urban owner–occupiers. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment* 30(1), 69–85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-014-9396-3>
- Smith, N. (2008) *Uneven Development: Nature, Capital, and the Production of Space*. The University of Georgia Press.
- Struyk, R. (2000). *Homeownership and housing finance policy in the former Soviet bloc - costly populism*. Research Report, Urban Institute.
- Sýkora, J., & Špačková, P. (2022). Neighbourhood at the crossroads: Differentiation in residential change and gentrification in a post-socialist inner-city neighbourhood. *Housing Studies* 37(5), 693–719. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2020.1829562>
- Vincze, E., & Zamfir, G.I. (2019). Racialised housing unevenness in Cluj-Napoca under capitalist redevelopment. *City. Analysis of urban trends, culture, theory, policy, action* 23(4-5), 439-460. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13604813.2019.1684078>
- Vincze, E. (2017) The ideology of economic liberalism and the politics of housing in Romania. *Studia Universitatis Babeș-Bolyai Sociologia* 62(3), pp. 29–54. <https://doi.org/10.24193/subbeuropaea.2017.3.02>
- Vincze, E. (2022) The mixed housing regime in Romanian state socialism. In A. Melegh (ed.), *Money, Markets, Socialisms. Papers presented at the conference titled 'Non-Capitalist Mixed Economies'* (pp. 26-45). Eszmélet Foundation.
- World Bank (1993) *Housing. Enabling markets to work*. Stand Alone Books.
- World Bank and Ministry of Development and Public Administration (2013) *Competitive Cities. Reshaping the Economic Geography of Romania*. Available at <https://www.worldbank.org/en/results/2014/04/11/reshaping-the-economic-geography-of-romania>. Accessed May 10, 2023.

- World Bank (2021) *Romania - Component 3: IUDS 2021-2030 - Housing Strategy Output 2: Report With Analysis of Demand and Supply of Housing, and Recommendations on How to Address the Gap between Demand and Supply - Supplementary Report: Situation Analysis*, Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group. Available at <https://documents.worldbank.org/e/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/099115010282233030/p172384068305a0bb087350914b8b1893ad>. Accessed May 10, 2023.
- Zamfir, G.I. (2021). Countering illegibility: a brief history of forced evictions in post-socialist Romania. *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai Sociologia* 1, 37-68. <https://10.2478/subbs-2022-0002>
- Zamfirescu, I., & Chelcea, L. (2021). Evictions as infrastructural events. *Urban Geography* 42(9), 1270–1291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2020.1778281>
- *** *Anuarul Statistic al României 1990* (1990). Institutul Național de Statistică.
- *** *Cluj Business*. The platform powered by the International Affairs and Investment Department within the Municipality of Cluj-Napoca. Available at <https://clujbusiness.ro/>. Accessed May 10, 2023.
- *** *Economia Clujului. Municipiul Cluj Napoca și Zona Metropolitană Cluj. Raport de cercetare – dezvoltarea economiei locale în deceniul 2008-2018* (2020). Centrul Interdisciplinar pentru Știința Datelor.
- *** *Economie Politică. Socialismul* (1978). Universitatea din București, Facultatea de Istorie-Filosofie, Catedra de Economie Politică, București.
- *** *Emerging Europe. Business-friendly city perception index* (2021). Available at <https://emerging-europe.com/reports/>. Accessed May 10, 2023.
- *** *Strategia Integrată de Dezvoltare Urbană 2021-2030*. Available at <https://primariaclujnapoca.ro/cetateni/centrul-de-inovare-si-imaginatie-civica/strategia-integrata-de-dezvoltara-urbana-sidu-2021-2030/>; also available at World Bank (2022) *Romania - Synthesis of SIDU Cluj-Napoca 2021-2030*, Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group, <https://shorturl.at/noqC3>; and World Bank (2022) *Romania - Component 3: IUDS 2021-2030 - Housing Strategy Output 1: Report With Analysis of Demand and Supply of Housing, and Recommendations on How to Address the Gap between Demand and Supply - Main Report: Key Takeaways and Path Forward*, Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group, <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/099115110282231024/p17238404d146f0f508eb0094ba6c1f9dff>. Accessed May 10, 2023.
- *** The Mayor.eu. Available at <https://www.themayor.eu/en/a/view/cluj-napoca-is-stepping-up-as-a-technology-hub-nicknamed-the-silicon-valley-of-eastern-europe-1320>. Accessed May 10, 2023.